

Correlation of Silage Feeds to Blood Biochemical Parameters in Saanen Goats

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Abstract:

This paper presents the results of monitoring blood biochemical parameters of Saanen goats when using some types of silage. The study was conducted on 40 Saanen goats 6-12 months old, with an average weight of 17.5 kg, raised at the Center for Livestock Biotechnology. The goats were completely randomized in blocks into 3 treatments (NT); NT1: pseudo-silage cashew nuts, NT2: silage cassava pulp and NT3: silage corn stalks and leaves and 1 control group (using standard feed at the center). Blood samples were taken

by jugular vein puncture of each animal in the morning, before feeding on days 1, 45 and 90 of the experiment. Blood biochemical indices: Glucose, Protein, Albumin, Globulin, BUN, Creatinine, AST, ALT, ALP, electrolyte index (Na, K, Ca, P) were measured by Abaxis Vetscan 2 chemical analyzer. Biochemical parameters of the control group and the 3 treatments 1, 2, 3 on the 90th day were respectively Glucose was 4.56 ± 2.86 ; 4.59 ± 3.84 ; 4.38 ± 3.88 ; 4.42 ± 3.18 mmol/l; Protein was 76.83 ± 8.56 ; 77.56 ± 6.82 ; 77.36 ± 7.96 ; 78.35 ± 8.38 g/l. The results of the evaluation of blood biochemical parameters of Saanen goats were all at normal levels when using silage rations. There was no statistical difference between the experimental and control groups. The results confirmed that the use of supplementary silage in Saanen goat farming did not affect blood biochemical indices. These data are useful for further studies on other ruminants, suggesting the use of silage in goat farming from agricultural by-products.

Keywords: *blood, biochemical parameters, Saanen goats, silage.*

Introduction

In recent years, in the context of global climate change, characterized by decreasing rainfall, especially in arid and semi-arid areas; along with increasing urbanization, reduced grazing land area, and reduced natural grass, has led to a decrease in the amount of traditional green forage for livestock (Foley et al., 2020). In this situation, establishing sustainable green forage production systems that are both productive and high quality, making full use of agricultural by-products, is extremely important in the context of the developing livestock industry (Xu et al.,

2021). In recent years, the growth rate of goat herds in Vietnam has been quite rapid, the scale of livestock farming has been expanded, and there is a tendency to develop into a farm economy in many provinces and cities. Bach Thao goat (BT) is the goat breed with the largest population in Vietnam. BT goats grow and develop quickly, are easy to raise, and can withstand high temperatures and hot sun. Feed (TA) is mainly natural leafy plants. BT goats do not compete with humans for food, TA is mainly leaves, grass, even straw and other agricultural by-products. BT goats make good use of raw green TA to transform into valuable products.

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Goats produce many products of economic and medical value (Bui, 2016). BT goats have the ability to endure hardship and resist diseases well, are easy to raise, rarely get sick, and are widely adapted to many regions in the country (Bui, 2016).

Preparing silage helps create food that can be stored for a long time, taking advantage of excess raw green food sources, ensuring diversity in food types, and improving the nutritional quality of livestock rations (Du et al., 2023). Due to the reduction in pasture area and the availability of forage in livestock production, there has been a significant increase in the import of large quantities of forage to compensate for the lack of high-quality feed sources. When considering costs, the use of silage emerges as a more practical option for production and use in arid or semi-arid regions (Taravat et al., 2017). The rational use of low-quality forage, after appropriate treatment, has the potential to significantly reduce feed costs without affecting production performance. Furthermore, this approach opens up new avenues for feeding low-quality forage to goats, thereby reducing feed costs without adversely affecting livestock productivity. Scientific studies have shown that judicious use and processing of forages can reduce the cost of concentrated feed consumption, contributing to the longevity, productivity and fertility of animals (Guo et al., 2022). The high digestibility of fiber in these forages can reduce the feeling of fullness in the gut, facilitating increased feed consumption and enhancing milk production (Wang et al., 2021). Furthermore, silage has been shown to be effective in reducing methane production and emissions (Khan et al., 2012).

In Vietnam, with the significant costs associated with the production, storage and import of dry forages, silage production is an effective strategy. There are many studies on the effects of silage on cattle growth parameters (Nguyen Hai Quan and Nguyen Xuan Ba, 2008); Nguyen Huu Van et al. (2008). Recently, there has been a study evaluating the effect of silage on growth parameters and blood physiology in Phan Rang sheep (Nguyen Duc Thinh et al., 2021; Nguyen Binh Phuong et al., 2023). On the other hand,

blood biochemical and physiological indices can be used to monitor and evaluate the health, nutritional and physiological status of ruminants (Al-Eissa et al., 2012). Among the influencing factors, nutrition has been reported to have a profound effect on the blood biochemical characteristics of small ruminants (Mohammed et al., 2016). Research on blood physiological and biochemical indices of Saanen goats has also been published by Nguyen Thi Thu Hien (2022). In this context, our hypothesis posits that silage supplementation can have a positive effect on the health and productivity of goats. Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of supplementing some silages (siled cashew nuts, silaged corn stalks, silaged cassava) on blood biochemical parameters of Saanen goats - an imported goat breed in Vietnam. Because hematological biochemical parameters are clear signs of the health status of animals that cannot be observed; therefore, evaluating the effects of silage diets on blood biochemical parameters of Saanen goats aims to provide reasonable recommendations for economic efficiency for the goat industry and to solve some environmental problems caused by by-products from some agricultural crops.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Animals

Saanen goats (6-12 months old), raised at the Center for Research and Development of Large Livestock, Bau Bang District, Binh Duong Province, Vietnam.

Some Foods

Cashew nut silage, corn stalk silage, wheat silage; green elephant grass, mixed bran (Tongwei belongs to TONWEI Vietnam Co., Ltd).

Tools

3cc blood collection syringe, EDTA anticoagulant tube, blood biochemistry analyzer (Abaxis Vetscan 2, Union City, CA, USA).

Experimental Layout

The experiment (TN) consisted of 40 goats (with a male-female ratio of 1:1; 6-12 months old),

arranged completely randomly in blocks into 3 treatments (T) and 1 control group (CT). The goats were kept separately in pens measuring 1.5×1.0m, with the symbol of T and the individual name attached to the pen wall. The goats were vaccinated, familiarized with the environment and experimental conditions for two weeks, followed by 90 days of the experiment.

The pens were shaded from the sun, and the feeding troughs were sprayed with disinfectant before being brought into the experiment. There was clean water for the goats to drink freely. The goat care process was carried out consistently in all the experiments. The goats were fed 4 times a day, at 6, 10, 14, and 16 o'clock. When feeding, the correct NT was determined and the feeding troughs were cleaned before feeding. The experiment was arranged according to tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Food Arrangement According to the Control Treatment

Feeding Time (hour)	Kind of Food	Weight (kg)
6	Synthetic bran	1
10	Green elephant grass	2
14	Synthetic bran	1
16	Green elephant grass	2

Table 2. Food Arrangement According to Treatment 1

Feeding Time (Hour)	Kind of Food		Weight (Kg)	
6	Silage	Synthetic bran	1	0,1
10	Green elephant grass		2	
14	Silage	Synthetic bran	1	0,1
16	Green elephant grass		2	

Note: Silage for each experiment 1, 2, 3 is respectively: Cashew silage, corn silage, cassava silage.

Blood Sampling Method

Blood samples are taken by jugular vein puncture of each animal in the morning (7-8am), before feeding.

Step 1-Fix the goat: Choose a fixed position close to the wall with support, preferably the corner of the cage (because goats often have the habit of retreating when fixed), use a piece of food to cover the eyes to prevent the goat from jumping forward.

Step 2-Determine the sampling location: The goat's head must be high and slightly tilted to one side so that the neck is curved, press the thumb into the jugular vein at the end of the neck to make the jugular vein appear, insert the needle

into the vein, push the needle along the vein, and aspirate 2-3ml of blood.

Step 3-Sample processing: After taking blood, the sample is quickly placed in an anticoagulant tube (EDTA), shake the anticoagulant solution gently, record the name, symbol of each individual, and date of sampling.

Step 4-Sample analysis: Samples were centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 10 minutes (Roto x 32®-Hettich). The centrifugation time was as soon as possible (less than 2 hours). Serum was collected and kept at -20°C for analysis. Blood biochemical indices were measured using a chemical analyzer (Abaxis Vetscan 2, Union City, CA, USA).

Blood biochemical indices analyzed: Total protein (g/l), Globulin (g/l), Albumin (g/l), Glucose (mmol/l), Blood urea nitrogen-BUN (mmol/l); Creatinine ($\mu\text{mol/l}$); Aspartate transaminase-AST (U/l); Alanine amino transferase-ALT (U/l); Alkaline phosphatase-ALP (U/l), Na (mmol/l), K (mmol/l), Ca (mmol/l), P (mmol/l), Cl (mmol/l).

Data Analysis

Statistical parameters were processed by MS-Excel 2020 software. Data was expressed as mean (Mean \pm SD). Analysis of ANOVA and Post hoc test with Tukey-Kramer test to evaluate the difference between groups ($P < 0.05$).

Results and Discussion

The results of monitoring the blood biochemical indicators of Saanen goats when using silage on days 1, 45 and 90 are shown in Tables 3, 4 and 5, respectively.

Table 3 shows that on the first day of the experiment, the protein content of treatments 1, 2, 3 fluctuated from 73.45-75.68g/L; Globulin was 44.68-45.61 g/L; Albumin was 27.94-28.67 g/L; Glucose content was 4.35-4.71 mmol/L; BUN was 3.56-3.64 mmol/L; Creatinine was 147.32-149.23 $\mu\text{mol/L}$; AST was 126.93-132.50 U/L. Although the highest concentration of each index could be at T1, 2 or T3, the difference between treatments was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$).

Table 3. Blood Biochemical Parameters of Saanen Goats at Day 1

Parameters	CT	T1	T2	T3
Protein, g/L	73.45 \pm 6.81	75.28 \pm 6.68	74.61 \pm 7.56	75.68 \pm 6.25
Globulin, g/L	45.61 \pm 4.83	44.86 \pm 4.36	45.34 \pm 5.73	44.68 \pm 5.66
Albumin, g/L	28.61 \pm 3.32	28.75 \pm 4.35	27.94 \pm 4.64	28.67 \pm 4.85
Glucose, mmol/L	4.35 \pm 1.15	4.71 \pm 1.26	4.48 \pm 2.38	4.62 \pm 2.33
BUN, mmol/L	3.56 \pm 1.08	3.63 \pm 1.25	3.57 \pm 1.32	3.64 \pm 1.47
Creatinine, $\mu\text{mol/L}$	147.32 \pm 11.53	147.54 \pm 11.01	149.23 \pm 10.56	148.66 \pm 9.68
AST, U/L	128.75 \pm 7.74	130.52 \pm 9.54	128.57 \pm 10.91	126.93 \pm 14.05
ALT, U/L	28.89 \pm 4.86	29.78 \pm 5.33	29.49 \pm 3.64	30.46 \pm 4.82
ALP, U/L	155.71 \pm 12.21	156.63 \pm 10.64	157.94 \pm 10.73	156.25 \pm 11.26
Na, mmol/L	154.85 \pm 7.78	153.57 \pm 6.23	152.96 \pm 8.75	155.14 \pm 7.88
K, mmol/L	4.86 \pm 0.97	4.95 \pm 1.24	4.92 \pm 0.93	4.97 \pm 1.09
Ca, mmol/L	2.86 \pm 0.90	2.91 \pm 0.85	2.89 \pm 0.91	2.82 \pm 0.86
P, mmol/L	2.32 \pm 0.78	2.63 \pm 0.86	2.38 \pm 0.92	2.46 \pm 0.78
Cl, mmol/L	105.83 \pm 10.51	107.67 \pm 9.94	107.48 \pm 8.76	107.56 \pm 5.83

The results in Table 4 show that after 45 days of using silage, the combination of silage into the diet had no significant effect on the concentrations of glucose, albumin, total protein and albumin to globulin ratio in plasma in Saanen goats ($P > 0.05$). The blood biochemical indices of goats with protein content in the treatments ranged from 74.65-76.61 g/l, Globulin content was 45.52-46.45 g/l; Albumin content was 26.94-28.65 g/l, Glucose content was 4.68-5.03 mmol/l. Blood biochemistry results after 45 days of feeding silage of 3 experimental groups and control group showed that the indices of Urea Nitrogen (BUN),

Creatinine, AST, ALT, ALP, Na, K, Ca, P were not statistically different in experimental groups ($P > 0.05$), the indices were within the normal range of goats (Merk, 2022), consistent with the blood physiology and chemistry indices of Saanen goats published by Nguyen (2022).

Table 5 presents the effect of replacing conventional roughage with silage on blood biochemical indices at the end of the 90-day experiment. Notably, no parameters were evaluated with significant differences ($P > 0.05$). Replacing roughage with silage had no statistically significant effect on these indices. Protein content of the experiments ranged from

76.83 to 78.35 g/L, Globulin content ranged from 47.21 (CT); 49.27 (T2); 29.15 (NT1), respectively; Albumin content was 28.46 (T2) g/l -31.96 g/L (T3); glucose content was 4.38 to 4.59 mmol/l. This result shows that the blood physiological indices are still within the normal limits as published by Merk (2022), ($P>0.05$). There is no significant change in the values of Na, K, Ca, P between the experimental groups

on sampling days 1, 45 and 90 of the experiment ($P>0.05$). When comparing these indices with the reference values of normal goats (Merk, 2022), they are all within the normal range of Saanen goats (Nguyen, 2022). Thus, this result demonstrated that after 90 days of feeding silage, there was no effect on the blood biochemical parameters of goats in all experimental groups.

Table 4. Blood Biochemical Parameters of Saanen Goats at Day 45

Parameters	CT	T1	T2	T3
Protein, g/L	75.83±6.16	76.61±5.81	74.65±6.64	76.23±6.37
Globulin, g/L	46.38 ±6.31	45.82±5.37	45.52±5.74	46.45±5.43
Albumin, g/L	27.67±5.87	28.65±4.82	26.94±5.18	27.07 ±6.53
Glucose, mmol/L	4.68 ±2.65	4.85±1.72	5.03±2.36	4.85±2.61
BUN, mmol/L	3.83±0.96	3.76±1.50	3.75±1.81	3.82±1.68
Creatinine, μmol/L	154.18±10.73	155.52±10.33	152.55±10.65	153.57±11.56
AST, U/L	135.85±10.86	133.52±11.11	134.65±11.46	136.85±11.52
ALT, U/L	32.84±4.78	31.54±4.82	32.15±3.36	33.03±4.53
ALP, U/L	157.53±10.55	158.63±11.65	156.51±11.24	156.62±11.32
Na, mmol/L	156.56± 6.65	155.71±6.68	157.73±6.49	155.63±7.81
K, mmol/L	4.95±0.87	5.28±1.23	5.16±0.96	4.97± 1.15
Ca, mmol/L	2.76±0.88	2.89±0.85	3.11±0.84	3.05±0.75
P, mmol/L	2.58±0.86	2.38±0.89	2.43±0.87	2.52±0.92
Cl, mmol/L	109.26±10.18	111.26±12.91	108.99±11.36	103.71±9.73

The results of this study are consistent with studies determining growth performance and some serum biochemical parameters in some cattle when using hay, silage, and corn silage as roughage sources (Bernes et al., 2008; Bernes and Stengärde, 2012). The source of silage did not affect the blood biochemical indices of the animals (Bernes et al., 2008). The source of roughage also did not affect the serum glucose concentration, total protein and albumin of the animals (Bernes et al., 2008). Bernes and

Stengärde (2012) reported that the live weight gain and feed intake did not differ between sheep fed hay or silage, and they also found that the live weight gain and feed intake of cattle fed hay were higher. Similarly, several studies in cattle have reported no differences in KL and KL gain when fed good quality forages or silage (Ayaşan et al., 2012); silage, corn silage and grass + corn silage (Juniper et al., 2005); alfalfa and corn silage (Kirkland and Patterson, 2006); or corn meal and beet silage (Browne et al., 2005).

Table 5. Blood Biochemical Parameters of Saanen Goats at Day 90

Parameters	CT	T1	T2	T3
Protein, g/L	76.83±8.56	77.56±6.82	77.36±7.96	78.35±8.38
Globulin, g/L	47.21 ±4.81	48.73±4.61	49.27±4.88	47.35±5.16
Albumin, g/L	30.63±4.95	29.54±5.66	28.61±6.54	31.96 ±5.34
Glucose, mmol/L	4.56 ±2.86	4.59±3.84	4.38±3.88	4.42±3.18
BUN, mmol/L	3.68±0.82	3.86±1.67	3.87±1.75	3.76±1.32
Creatinine, μmol/L	158.68±10.87	155.95±11.98	156.39±11.67	154.93±10.34
AST, U/L	133.78±11.35	128.82±9.93	129.86±10.45	122.45±11.05
ALT, U/L	32.56±6.67	33.58±5.88	33.43±6.36	33.61±6.35
ALP, U/L	155.92±10.56	156.38±11.46	157.54±10.66	154.39±10.57

Na, mmol/L	150.25± 6.82	151.68±7.85	149.91±7.78	151,83±10.49
K, mmol/L	4.98±0.83	4.91±1.02	4.89±0.96	4.85± 0.57
Ca, mmol/L	3.15±0.66	3.17±0.79	3.41±0.73	3.12±0.88
P, mmol/L	2.75±0.84	2.86±0.91	2.87±0.92	2.92±0.76
Cl, mmol/L	114.25±10.74	112.63±10.51	110.64±11.07	112.83±9.63

In this study, the incorporation of silage into the diet had no significant effect on plasma glucose, albumin, total protein, and albumin and globulin ratios in Saanen goats (Tables 5, 6, 7) ($P > 0.05$). However, according to the study by Shohre et al. (2023), in Mahabadi goats fed a diet including corn silage, a significant decrease in plasma urea nitrogen (BUN) concentration was observed ($P = 0.01$). Wang et al. (2016), also reported that dietary corn silage supplementation did not affect serum glucose and total protein concentrations but increased serum triglyceride concentrations. In contrast, in the study by Wang et al. (2021), a decrease in BUN concentration was found when alfalfa/hay was replaced by corn silage, this trend in plasma urea nitrogen concentration was consistent with the results for milk urea nitrogen. This difference may be attributed to the synchronous availability of both protein and energy in the rumen (Khaing et al., 2015). The use of corn silage, with its high starch content and energy supply, may have been a contributing factor to the observed decrease in rumen nitrogen concentration. However, it is worth noting that Wang et al. (2016) also reported that there was no significant effect on blood urea nitrogen concentration when lactating goats were fed a diet containing corn silage.

Studies on the effects of silaged cassava pulp also showed positive effects in ruminants in Vietnam (Nguyen and Nguyen, 2008; Nguyen Huu Van et al., 2008). A recent study, a study on the effects of silage on growth parameters of Phan Rang sheep also showed that goats had normal growth rates when using silage (Nguyen et al., 2021); in which the 90th day weight in the treatments ranged from 19-19.9 kg, with no statistically significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between treatments and compared to the control. Silage also does not affect the blood physiological parameters of Phan Rang sheep (Nguyen et al., 2023). Recently, the results of

evaluating the blood biochemical parameters of Bach Thao goats when using some types of silage also showed that the biochemical parameters of the control group and the 3 treatments 1, 2, 3 on the 90th day were respectively Glucose was 4.20 ± 2.52 ; 4.12 ± 3.88 ; 4.13 ± 3.61 ; 4.21 ± 3.61 mmol/l; Protein was 76.58 ± 7.60 ; 77.61 ± 6.82 ; 75.59 ± 8.15 ; 78.50 ± 7.81 g/l; Albumin was 29.68 ± 3.29 ; 30.15 ± 5.11 ; 29.46 ± 5.12 ; 28.96 ± 5.32 g/l; BUN was 2.76 ± 0.95 ; 2.81 ± 1.01 ; 2.82 ± 1.22 ; 2.74 ± 1.32 mmol/l; Creatinine was 136.36 ± 10.88 ; 135.75 ± 11.83 ; 137.35 ± 11.26 ; 135.96 ± 12.25 $\mu\text{mol/l}$; AST was 106.57 ± 8.81 ; 107.82 ± 10.01 ; 107.66 ± 11.34 ; 108.44 ± 10.62 U/l; ALT was 31.24 ± 6.16 ; 31.75 ± 4.82 ; 30.94 ± 4.58 ; 31.58 ± 4.33 U/l. The results of evaluating the blood biochemical parameters of goats were at normal levels when using silage rations. There was no statistical difference between the groups and the control (Nguyen, 2024). Thus, based on the results of other studies and the results of this study, it shows that the use of corn, cassava and cashew nut silage as a source of roughage does not affect the health of Saanen goats.

Conclusion

The addition of corn silage to the diet as a replacement for conventional forage showed no significant differences in blood biochemical parameters in Saanen goats. Therefore, the use of silage is recommended due to its benefits, especially in areas with limited access to forage. These findings provide valuable insights into the potential benefits of incorporating corn silage as a forage replacement for goats. This study contributes to the expansion of our existing knowledge and provides additional dietary recommendations for goats.

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